

Synthesis and Biological Study of a New Precocene Analogue on *Chrysocoris stollii*

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The concept of controlling insects with juvenile hormone antagonists which act in an opposite manner to juvenoids has attracted much attention since early seventies. Compounds possessing AJH activity can cause precocious metamorphosis, resulting in mortality of susceptible insects as prematurely formed pupae or defective adults. A further advantage of compounds with AJH activity lies in their capacity to compress the destructive larval stages of phytophagous insects and thus significantly reducing the damage to food and fibre crops.

Precocenes (1 and 2) have been shown to be anti-*allatotropins* which induce precocious metamorphosis in insects and are potential insecticides¹. These chromenes have been found to interfere in the production of juvenile hormones². The metabolic fate of precocenes has been extensively studied³ and the role of double bond in the oxygen heterocycle has been shown to be responsible partly, if not wholly, for the precocious metamorphosis in insects. Here we report the synthesis and biological activity of the precocene analogue, 2,2-dimethyl-3,4-cyclopenteno [5,6]benzo-3-chromene⁴ (4) on *Chrysocoris stollii*.

Compound 4 has no methoxy function and if the presence of a MeO group in precocenes is responsible for the AJH activity, this compound must be inactive. The *in vivo* epoxidation of the double bond is expected to be difficult as the double bond is tetra-substituted.

Scheme 1

Results and Discussion

3,4-Cyclopenten[5,6]benzocoumarin (3) was prepared by condensing 2-naphthol and ethyl cyclopentenone-2-carboxylate in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid (Scheme 1). The ir spectrum of 3 showed the presence of a lactone carbonyl group (1700 cm⁻¹). In the pmr spectrum, the methylene (a) of compound 3 appeared at δ 3.5 as a triplet in the downfield region due to the presence of a carbonyl group, but the methylene (b) protons appeared at δ 2.14 as a multiplet due to two methylene (a and c) and the two protons of methylene (c) appeared as a triplet at δ 2.85 relatively downfield with respect to methylene (b) protons. The six aromatic protons appeared in the range δ 7.14–8.48.

2,2-Dimethyl[3,4]cyclopenteno[5,6]benzo-3-chromene (4) was obtained by the action methyl magnesium iodide on 3. In ir spectrum of 4 the C=C band appeared at 1615 cm⁻¹ but the band at 1700 cm⁻¹ completely disappeared indicating the absence of carbonyl group. The ¹H nmr showed the six aromatic protons at δ 7.07–8.21. The C-2 methyl protons appeared at δ 1.45 as a singlet and the protons of three methyl-

ene groups appeared at different positions : methylene (c) protons appeared at δ 3.26 as a triplet, probably due to the diamagnetic current of the ring and the methylene (b) protons appeared at δ 2.14 as a multiplet, but the methylene (a) protons appeared at δ 2.15 as a triplet. In the mass spectrum, the M^+ ion appeared at m/z 250 with relative intensity 14%. The base peak ion 235 (m/z), is probably stabilised due to long conjugation with naphthalene ring.

In order to verify the premises regarding the precocene analogue synthesised during the present investigation, some simple experiments were performed on the insect *Chrysocoris stollii* (order Hemiptera), a pest on the wild plant, *Croton banoplandianum* (family Euphorbiaceae). The compound in acetone solution (10 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$) was topically applied on the ventral part of the thoracic region of 3rd, 4th and 5th instar in dosages 2.5, 2.5 and 5.0 μl respectively. The time taken by the nymphs for their metamorphic development into adults is given in Table I.

TABLE I

Compd	3rd instar h	4th instar h	5th instar h
Acetone(control)	92-100	135-142	260-266
Compound 4	112-116	170-174	338-342

It is evident that metamorphic development was delayed in relation to control, which is contrary to the hitherto reported biological activity of precocenes which induce precocious metamorphosis in insects. Besides, all the nymphal stages showed appreciable loss of weight and appetite as reported earlier by Bowers *et al.*¹.

A more detailed study is in progress to assess the morphological and physiological changes.

Experimental

3,4-Cyclopenteno[5,6]benzocoumarin (3) : To a well-stirred solution of 2-naphthol (7.2 g, 0.05 mol) and ethyl cyclopentenone-2-carboxylate (15.6 g, 0.1 mol) in sodium-dry benzene (100 ml), concentrated H_2SO_4 (15 ml) was added dropwise. The stirring was

continued for about 20 h when a deep green colouration appeared. The reaction mixture was then neutralised with saturated NaHCO_3 solution and the benzene layer separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with benzene (5 $\times$ 100 ml) and the combined extracts washed with brine, dried and concentrated under reduced pressure. The solid residue was crystallised from ethanol and then recrystallised from chloroform-ethanol, (5.32 g, 45%), m.p. 195°; λ_{max} (MeOH) 215, 232, 250, 303, 316, 343, 359; ν_{max} (nujol) 2 920, 2 860, 1 715, 1 610, 1 590, 1 550, 1 510, 1 455, 1 380, 1 350, 1 300, 1 275, 1 240, 1 225, 1 210, 1 198, 1 150, 1 120, 1 090, 1 075, 1 062, 1 040, 1 008, 995, 985, 880, 860, 820, 810, 780, 770, 722, 710, 675, 645, 590, 540, 490; δ (CDCl_3) 3.5 (2H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 2.85 (2H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 2.14 (2H, q), 8.32 (1H, d), 8.76 (1H, d), 7.34-7.62 (2H, m); m/z 236 (M^+ , 100).

2,2-Dimethyl-3,4-cyclopenteno[5,6]benzo-3-chromene : It was prepared by the reported procedure⁵ by the action of 3 (590 mg, 2.5 mmol) in freshly distilled dry tetrahydrofuran (25 ml) with CH_3MgI under nitrogen atmosphere for 4 h at 0° and then left overnight. The resulting solid was decomposed with saturated ammonium chloride solution containing dilute HCl (pH 4.5). Usual work-up and column chromatography over silica gel (60-120 mesh) yielded the product, (437 mg, 70%), m.p. 95° (pet. ether, b.p. 60-80°); λ_{max} (MeOH) 202, 246, 304, 317, 350 nm; ν_{max} (nujol) 2 920, 2 860, 1 614, 1 590, 1 555, 1 500, 1 455, 1 380, 1 340, 1 290, 1 252, 1 230, 1 198, 1 153, 1 120, 1 090, 1 070, 1 050, 780, 775, 770, 740, 720, 695, 670, 740, 580, 562, 550 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 8.21 (1H, d), 7.7 (1H, dd), 7.58 (1H, d), 7.36 (1H, m), 7.25 (1H, m), 7.07 (1H, d), 3.25 (2H, t), 2.52 (2H, t), 2.11 (2H, m), 1.45 (6H s); m/z 250 (M^+ , 14), 235 (-15, 100%).

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